

AFFECTIVE DECISIONS AND RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

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BACKGROUND

The rationale behind recommender systems is that people make rational decisions based on the available information they have in a particular context. However, substantial experimental data show that what people think, like, need or want is often influenced by the way their options are framed, deviating their ‘rationality’. We aim to explore some principles of behavioral economics in the design of recommender systems through an empirical study based on a smart phone application purposely customized for the 9th Design and Emotion conference.

A rational decision is such that maximizes someone’s current situation yet avoiding loses. Many situations of everyday life show that people often make “irrational” decisions because they make choices that procure greater benefits to others than to themselves. Such ‘irrational’ behavior might be defined in terms of cognitive biases and judgmental heuristics (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

From a comprehensive literature review of behavioral economics Pfarr and Gregory (Pfarr & Gregory, 2010) characterized seven relevant behavioral tendencies in decision-making. These behavioral tendencies are clusters of literature that have circulated significantly in behavioral economics discussions, and that they argue are relevant to design research. We find Context-Dependent Preferences and Affective-Cognitive Decision Making tendencies particularly relevant for the design of computational recommender systems. Context-Dependent

Preferences is the tendency in which people prefer intermediate options rather than those located at the extremes of a continuum (Simonson & Tversky, 1992). Context-Dependent Preferences are also related to the location of appealing or unappealing items in relation to each other. People perceive paired options with the same attractiveness as less appealing than the same options evaluated independently, but people perceive an attractive option as more appealing if it is paired with a non-attractive option (Hsee & LeClerc, 1998). Affective-Cognitive Decision Making is the tendency of people in situations of scarce information to follow their affective reactions rather than their cognitive reactions (Shiv & Fedorikhin, 1999).

The smart phone application to be ran in conference attendees’ phones was developed in the Fall semester of 2013 using the database of presentations and the schedule of the 7th Design and Emotion Conference, held in Chicago in 2010. For the workshop we will use the schedule and database of presentations of the 9th Design and Emotion Conference. The application, named Day Book, allows users to program their conference schedule and share it with other registered attendees. The user has two ways of picking a presentation: by topic preference or by schedule availability. Moreover, the attendee can fine-tune the system’s recommendation by checking the name of the speaker or the list of potential attendees to a given presentation. Such list of potential attendees is updated on the fly as people subscribe or unsubscribe to the presentation. The interface design takes into consideration the two behavioral tendencies mentioned above to present the recommended results.

Figure 1. Screenshots of the application displaying the list of presentations recommended by the system based on the attendee's preferred topics and availability. It presents some examples of the lowest decision making level of navigation. Source: the authors.

The general usability and task accomplishment of the application has been tested with seven users yielding very satisfactory results. However, the subjects in the user tests were not very familiar with the dynamics of parallel tracks conferences.

GOAL

We want to use D&E2014 as a living laboratory to explore three aspects of the application:

1. In what degree are academic attendees biased by popularity when choosing a presentation from an offered schedule?
2. In what degree are the choices of academic attendees influenced by the displayed schedule?
3. Is the user interface clear enough to help attendees to program their schedules?

The application will be a fully working prototype; therefore it would be a valuable tool for attendees to program their schedule and for organizers to make a post-mortem evaluation of the conference.

APPROACH

This workshop does not need a specific location; it is open to everyone who wants to install the application in his/her mobile phone, and could be held simultaneously in the three cities of the conference.

Potential attendees will be encouraged to download and install the app in their phones some days before or at their arrival to the conference. This could be a way to entice people to register specially if they are in Bogotá.

We would like to have a desk at the registration booth in Bogotá to inform people about the app and present some visualization of the conference's dynamics at the closing ceremony.

Users will be asked to accept the terms and conditions of installing the application. There will be a crystal-clear notification of the type and amount of data they will disclose to the workshop organizers and how we will guarantee the confidentiality of the data collected. We foresee that we are collecting only attendees names, conference ID, presentations marked as "I will attend", e-mail, website, affiliation.

The data collected will be used to study how some data structures such as lists and the organization of items in the list affect people's decisions. It will also be used to study the evolution of the presentation's popularity.

The app is not intended to advertise any organization.

NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

As many as registered attendees who download the app.

PLANNED LENGTH

The official days go from October 6-10, but since the app will be available one week before the conference begins, the total length would be ten days.

PREFERRED CITY

There is no need to be at a specific location. We would like to have a representative at the registration desk in Bogotá. We will also have a booth in Cali.

MATERIALS

Attendees smart phones, application, iOS, and Android compilers. Universidad Icesi will provide the server and other technological facilities.

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